

Educational environment of shaping conflict resolution skills at the tertiary level

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ABSTRACT

As the modern world is characterized by a large number of various conflicts, it is vital for people to resolve them peacefully. So, it is relevant to develop conflict resolution skills while educating students. The research aimed to examine how certain educational environments designed to cultivate conflict resolution skills influence the development of these skills level. A total of 139 students of a Ukrainian university, consisted of two experimental group (E1=48; E2=46) and a control group (C=45) participated in the experiment and produced significant findings that are crucial to the field of conflict resolution skills development. The χ^2 test helped analyses the experiment data and make a conclusion about its statistical significance. The p-value (less than 0.05) indicated that the difference between the experimental and control groups was statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed that the students of the experimental groups had substantially higher achievements than the control group students. Thus, educational environments designed to cultivate conflict resolution skills effectively influence these skills level development if academic staff purposefully promotes it. It is recommended to utilize the proposed educational environments in complex within formal educational settings, during extracurricular activities and internships.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's crisis world, the average person often has to deal with complex conflict situations, which arise both in the professional sphere and in everyday life, as well as to face the moral consequences of these situations [1]. So, it is essential to prepare people to deal with conflicts and adequately resolve them when conflicts arise. It is obvious that this task should be given to higher educational institutions. So, conflict resolution skills development while teaching students is relevant. The question arises: what can help develop these skills at the tertiary level, and to what extent. We decided to investigate this problem based on the vocational training of lawyers-to-be because employees in the legal field face even more significant challenges due to the inherent stress and socio-psychological tension associated with their work. The nature of lawyers' responsibilities often leads to heightened stress levels, and workers in the law sphere frequently encounter various conflicts while performing their duties. Consequently, during the vocational training of law students, it is imperative to prioritize the development of conflict resolution skills, which may be defined as the ability that empowers an individual to swiftly, respectfully, and efficiently address conflicts. These skills

equip a person to navigate challenging professional interactions successfully, accurately assess the conflict's nature, manage negative emotional states affecting adversaries, and undertake actions aimed at preventing or resolving conflicts effectively [2].

The subject under examination is also relevant because modern employers [3], [4] highly appreciate and even demand well-honed soft skills, particularly conflict resolution abilities. However, nowadays, conflict management and resolution training of students in higher educational institutions of any profile (at least in most countries) is not considered mandatory, generally has a fragmentary, diffuse nature and does not provide the appropriate level of development of conflict resolution skills in students. So, the question of educational environments that may help these skills shaping has not been developed sufficiently. We conducted this investigation to shed some light on the lacunes that exist in the design of proper educational environments, which are necessary for developing conflict resolution skills during the teaching and learning process at the tertiary level. So, the novelty of our research is in complex development of educational environments that shape future lawyers' conflict resolution skills both in classroom and extracurricular activities that was proved experimentally.

The capacity to manage and resolve conflicts is considered one of a person's soft skills, i.e., personal qualities that facilitate effective and harmonious interaction with others. Since today, the development of soft skills is of great significance numerous studies explore soft skills from various interdisciplinary perspectives and their relevance to the training of future professionals. So, specific cases of soft skills development across different countries have been presented by Mwita *et al.* [5] in Tanzania; Fadhil *et al.* [6], Ahmad *et al.* [7] in Pakistan; Caggiano *et al.* [8] in Italy and Finland; Yan *et al.* [9] in China. Describing their experience, the mentioned authors are not concerned with the educational environments necessary for developing those soft skills. There are pedagogical investigations of the problem under study that are connected with specific educational environments and instructional approaches aimed at fostering soft skills [10]–[12]. However, these manuscripts do not deal with conflict resolution skills development. Some researchers consider the cultivation of competencies, which are necessary for developing conflict resolution skills, in particular communicative competencies [13], intercultural competence [14], team building competence [15], and social and emotional competence [16]. Nevertheless, the stated works are not focused on conflict resolution skills development either.

A great number of studies dealing with soft skills development are of a psychological nature. Especially it concerns conflict management and resolution skills. Scholars contemplate these skills from different aspects: i) define conflicts as situations that appear between two interconnected parties, experiencing strong emotions, with seemingly incompatible outcomes or beliefs, where at least one party recognizes the incompatibility and views it as problematic [2]; ii) single out positive and negative consequences of conflicts [2]; iii) consider specific conflict outcomes connected with emotional energy [17]; and iv) distinguish models of conflicts and study conflict management and resolution, namely: principles of successful conflict resolution, models, stages and strategies of conflict resolution [18]. For example, some principles and techniques for general psychological training of future law enforcement officers can be found in the work of Shvets *et al.* [19]. Partial coverage of resolving conflicts constructively in the professional law environment is studied by several researchers [20]–[27]. However, despite a great number of investigations the practical elements of conflict resolution training for aspiring lawyers have not been thoroughly elucidated in them, and the educational environments for effectively cultivating conflict resolution skills in future lawyers remain undeveloped. So, the purpose of the article is to examine how certain educational environments designed to cultivate conflict resolution skills in future lawyers influence the development of these skills levels. The tasks of the research are: i) To find out definitions of the key concepts of the investigation, in particular: “conflict” and “conflict resolution skills”; ii) To single out main components of the concept “conflict resolution skills” and to select questionnaires and tests suitable for assessing the levels of these components development in respondents; iii) To determine educational environments that could be appropriate for developing conflict resolution skills while teaching aspiring lawyers; and iv) To conduct a pedagogical experiment directed at cultivating conflict resolution skills in law students under certain educational environments.

2. METHOD

The study's conceptual framework is based on five methodological approaches in the pedagogical science. We used the constructivist approach to emphasize the role of social, cultural and cognitive processes in the common mechanisms of conflict situations. We utilized the communicative approach to form tools as a type of communication and interaction between individuals. The systematic approach was applied to take into account certain criteria as main components of conflict resolution skills and tools to create effective strategies that interact with each other, with surroundings, and other strategies. The personally oriented approach helped us to focus on the individuality development accordingly to social requirements to her or his abilities,

a self-awareness, revealed opportunities to establish self-recognition, self-realization and self-confidence. The activity-based approach was used as it proves the inseparability of activity and professional education, due to the practical knowledge, abilities and skills of the future lawyer are productively formed.

To fulfill the study's purpose, we employed the following research methods: i) Analysis and synthesis of scientific and methodological literature on the problem under investigation. With their help we could, firstly, understand the essence of the concepts such as "conflict" and "conflict resolution skills"; secondly, determine main components of the concept "conflict resolution skills", criteria and indicators; thirdly, select questionnaires and tests appropriate for assessing the levels of the determined components development in respondents; fourthly, fix educational environments, which would be sufficient for developing conflict resolution skills in future lawyers; ii) As the research purpose required operating with the empirical data to evaluate the level of conflict resolution skills development in our participants, among general scientific empirical methods we used observation, questionnaire, testing, and pedagogical experiment; and iii) Statistical processing methods built into Excel add-ins, as a chi-test and analysis of variance, to analyze the obtained categorized data on the levels of conflict resolution skills in order to identify patterns and to test null-hypothesis about the statistically significant differences between control and experimental groups at the beginning and the end of the experiment.

2.1. Study participants

To achieve the research purpose the pedagogical experiment was conducted on the basis of Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University (Kharkiv, Ukraine). It included 139 third and fourth-year students of 19-21 years old, divided into two experimental groups: E1 (consisting of 48 students) and E2 (comprising 46 students), along with one control group (C) consisting of 45 students. Respondents were selected from the sample using the nest sampling method, which involves choosing entire academic groups as research units instead of individual respondents. The gender distribution was 52.17% male and 47.82% female participants for E1 and 54.16% male and 45.83% female students for E2. Specially designed educational environments were purposefully and systematically created in experimental group E1 for training in classes and internships. Still, in experimental group E2, these environments were expanded to include extracurricular educational activities. The control group students were of the same age and consisted of 51.11% male and 48.88% female respondents. Their classes were conducted without purposeful implementation of the determined educational environments. The students were informed about all the features of the study and agreed to participate in it.

2.2. Organization of the study

During the research, it was hypothesized that the effectiveness of conflict resolution skills development in future lawyers would increase if academic staff cultivates these skills purposefully under certain educational environments. So, after analysis of research literature and pedagogical experiences, we proposed to test the following educational environments: i) Establishing a cultural atmosphere focused on fostering humane principles, promoting general cultural development, and enhancing ethical and volitional students' potentials (such as conflict flexibility, tolerance, patience, responsibility, and discipline); ii) Providing future lawyers with a solid theoretical foundation in conflict resolution knowledge to support the acquisition of related competence; and iii) Creating educational cases directed to facilitating the mastery of conflict resolution skills by learners during different kinds of vocational learning activities (both within formal educational settings and during extracurricular activities, as well as during internships). To assess the research hypothesis, a pedagogical experiment was carried out. It comprised three stages: i) the statement stage; ii) the formative stage; and iii) the control stage.

During the statement stage of the experiment, students from both the experimental (E1, E2) and control (C) groups underwent an assessment to determine their baseline level of conflict resolution skills. To check this level, we defined certain criteria as main components of conflict resolution skills based, firstly, on the idea of a skill as a person's ability to carry out certain activities based on acquired knowledge and competencies, the final stage of development of the action, mastering which allows the person to switch from one mode of action to another, to diversify methods of activity; secondly, considering the capacity to resolve conflicts by future lawyers is construed as an integrative intellectual endeavor of the prospective lawyer, which is demonstrated by the ability to mitigate opposition between conflicting parties, address the underlying issues that precipitate the conflict, and resolve disputes while adhering to the rule of law principles; thirdly, basing on personally oriented approach to shaping an effective lawyer personality. In our research, these criteria are: i) criterion related to motivation and personal attributes; ii) criterion related to intellectual and cognitive abilities; and iii) criterion related to procedural and reflexive skills.

In order to assess each criterion more accurately we also singled out indicators of each criterion, in particular: i) For criterion related to motivation and personal attributes—understanding the importance of conflict resolution skills as a vital aspect of the professionalism expected from contemporary lawyers;

aspiration to acquire proficiency in conflict resolution skills; personal traits that enhance the effective cultivation of conflict resolution skills in law students, such as resilience in handling conflicts, adaptability in decision-making, improvisational skills, empathy, emotional stability, teamwork, tolerance, and self-discipline in conflict scenarios; ii) For criterion related to intellectual and cognitive abilities—intellectual and diagnostic indicator, constructive and prognostic indicator; and iii) For criterion related to procedural and reflexive skills—communicative reflexivity in conflict situations, emotional reflexivity in conflict situations, reflexivity of behavior in conflict situations.

To assess the level of conflict resolution skills development at the beginning and the end of the experiment, the following diagnostic methods were utilized: i) “simplified personal questionnaire procedure” [28] in order to assess the following indicators: understanding the importance of conflict resolution skills as a vital aspect of the professionalism expected from contemporary lawyers; aspiration to acquire proficiency in conflict resolution skills; ii) “creativity questionnaire” [29] for assessing personal traits that enhance the effective cultivation of conflict resolution skills in law students, such as resilience in handling conflicts, adaptability in decision-making, improvisational skills, empathy, emotional stability, teamwork, tolerance, and self-discipline in conflict scenarios; iii) express questionnaire “tolerance index” [30] to assess intellectual and diagnostic indicator, constructive and prognostic indicator; and iv) “the perceived leadership communication questionnaire” [31] for assessing such indicators as communicative reflexivity in conflict situations, emotional reflexivity in conflict situations, reflexivity of behavior in conflict situations. Employing a range of diagnostic methods at the beginning of the experiment revealed that a significant portion of students in both the experimental and control groups lacked adequate development in conflict resolution skills. The data collected during the statement stage were considered in subsequent experimental endeavors.

The formative stage of the experiment aimed to enhance the proficiency of conflict resolution skills among prospective lawyers and entailed a diverse approach to the work structure. In experimental group E1, the effectiveness of educational environments in student training and internships was assessed. In experimental group E2, these environments were extended to extracurricular educational activities. The control group C did not receive specific educational environments aimed at fostering the development of conflict resolution skills among future lawyers. However, in the curricula of the students from both the experimental and the control groups there were the same subjects. Consequently, we can suppose that the second educational environment was applied partly in the control group too.

In the first educational environment, the following objectives need to be addressed: fostering harmonious interpersonal relationships among participants in the learning process, establishing a conducive socio-psychological atmosphere, and maintaining the aesthetic quality of the subject’s spatial environment. To achieve this goal, deans of the faculties where the experiment took place, along with academic staff and group moderators, directed their efforts towards fostering a supportive psychological atmosphere within the faculty and classrooms. They ensured the establishment of conducive conditions for developing communication styles among future lawyers grounded in mutual respect and tolerance. This laid the foundation for identifying professional and personal attributes conducive to conflict-free interactions and mitigated communication’s potential for conflict, thereby facilitating the cultivation of conflict resolution skills. In facilitating communication and interaction, professors also endeavored to counteract the influence of detrimental factors such as anxiety, breaches of pedagogical sensitivity by academic staff, and learning overburdens on the mental well-being of law students.

The second educational environment, aimed at equipping future lawyers with a robust theoretical foundation in conflict resolution, involved the integration of specialized topics and conflictology modules into the curriculum of social sciences and humanities lectures. To adhere to this requirement, the existing curricula were scrutinized, and classes suitable for the integration of this knowledge were identified. To enhance the theoretical education of students regarding conflict resolution, topics related to the role of conflicts in personal development and social dynamics, communication’s content, functions, and styles, as well as personal attributes influencing conflict propensity, were incorporated into social and humanitarian disciplines such as “legal psychology,” “professional and psychological training of lawyers,” “political science,” and “philosophy.” Furthermore, a dedicated course titled “conflict resolution competence for lawyers” was devised. Its implementation served two main purposes: firstly, to eliminate redundancy in educational content that students encountered across socio-humanitarian and professional disciplines, and secondly, to employ diverse, primarily interactive, teaching methods aimed at enhancing educational engagement and cognitive processes in acquiring knowledge of conflict resolution. To foster an interest in and necessity for conflict resolution knowledge, various teaching methods and tools were employed, including business games, storytelling, brainstorming, mini-discussions, problem-solving tasks, and the incorporation of real-life examples and legal practice anecdotes during instruction. This approach enhanced the integration of conflict resolution knowledge with the intricacies of the legal profession, prompting future lawyers to engage in critical thinking and make independent decisions when addressing diverse conflict scenarios.

In pursuit of the third educational environment for fostering conflict resolution skills among our students, we crafted diverse educational cases as part of their vocational training. Type I cases were designed to evoke emotional responses that encouraged our students to recognize professional and ethical attributes, emotional intelligence, and empathy (instances involving compassion, empathy, and challenges to established methods and outcomes). Type II cases aimed to promote conflict-free communication and foster creative collaboration in group settings among future law professionals (scenarios involving assistance, competition, rivalry, and hierarchical structures). Type III cases directly prompted students to recognize various aspects of conflict resolution skills (instances involving moral dilemmas, responsible decision-making, conflicts arising from professional and ethical considerations, and scenarios focused on mastering new conflict resolution techniques). Type IV cases were employed to encourage participants in the experiment to enhance their conflict resolution skills through self-improvement (situations involving criticism and self-criticism, conflicts between aspiring to adhere to professional and ethical standards and practical limitations, and scenarios addressing self-esteem issues, among others).

When discussing teaching methodologies for crafting educational cases, it was found that business games, role-playing, and simulation games proved to be effective tools for replicating situations and processes that closely mirror the realities of contemporary lawyers' professional duties. Throughout the experiment, modern communication technologies and multimedia instructional aids were extensively utilized. Moreover, while creating cases of interaction in order for our students to develop their conflict resolution skills, we used a variety of exercises: analytical, intellectual and prognostic, perceptual-empathic, communicative, emotional-regulatory, training exercises, constructive, and reflexive.

Additionally, internships at The Prosecutor's Office of Ukraine, The Security Service of Ukraine, and The Service of Execution of Court Decisions were incorporated after the third and fourth years of study to cultivate conflict resolution skills among aspiring lawyers. These internships provided students with real-world exposure to professional responsibilities, offering them invaluable opportunities to acquire hands-on experience in conflict resolution. During the control stage of the experiment, students from both the experimental and control groups underwent an evaluation to assess their ultimate level of conflict resolution skills development.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

At the statement stage of our experiment, in order to ensure the correctness of the hypothesis about the impact of our methodology, we checked the homogeneity of the groups that participated in the experiment according to the previously mentioned indicators of conflict resolution skills. For this case, we used the χ^2 test, which is an effective nonparametric tool for comparing the frequency-independent sample distribution in categorical data (in our study, the skill level categories). Their distribution does not follow the law of normal distribution, and this method is also appropriate for assessing the statistical significance of differences. Therefore, comparing the frequencies between the experimental and control groups before the experiment, we found that the overall χ^2 value was 0.007. The calculated by Excel tools p-value is 0.934 (for the χ^2 statistic with 1 degree of freedom). It is significantly higher than 0.05 (the significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ was taken as the generally accepted threshold for determining statistical significance). Thus, at the beginning of the experiment, our groups were homogeneous and there were no significant differences in the levels of conflict resolution skills between them. In addition, the expected frequency calculation for the experimental and control groups revealed their equality. The mentioned indicates that both groups are similar in terms of initial indicators and increase the validity of conclusions about the impact effectiveness, and our results are representative. Moreover, since our experimental group consisted of two subgroups, we conducted a similar analysis in the experimental subgroups E1 and E2. The value of $p=0.882$ (for $\chi^2=0.022$ with 1 degree of freedom) is significantly higher than 0.05, i.e., our experimental subgroups do not have significant differences; the subgroups are homogeneous. A comparative analysis of the results for the distribution of the experimental and control student groups according to the levels of conflict resolution skills development at the beginning and at the end of the experiment is presented in Figure 1.

Thus, the analysis of the diagram evidences that at the beginning of the experiment, students of both the experimental and control groups demonstrated a lack of a high-level development of conflict resolution skills, but at the end of the experiment, significant improvement in the development of these skills can be seen. The students of the experimental groups have substantially higher achievements than the control group students. It proves that educational environments designed to cultivate conflict resolution skills in future lawyers effectively influence the development of these skills level if academic staff promotes it purposefully.

The statistical analysis of the results obtained after our experiment was conducted by the χ^2 test. The contingency table containing the actual and expected values was created. The total value of $\chi^2=15.4$ and

the corresponding p-value, $p=0.000457$ (for χ^2 statistics with 2 degrees of freedom) using Excel's built-in functions were calculated. As we can see, the p-value is significantly less than 0.05; it indicates that the difference between the experimental and control groups is statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the approach we have implemented is an effective way to develop relevant skills.

Based on the defined criteria and indicators, notably more noteworthy changes were observed among students in the experimental groups compared to those in the control group. This observation provides sufficient evidence to confirm the hypothesis. Specifically, the experimental group E2 exhibited notably more substantial positive progress across all defined criteria. The distribution by levels of conflict resolution skills development in future lawyers of experimental (E1, E2) and control (C) groups at the statement and the control stages of the pedagogical experiment is demonstrated in Table 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of comparative and generalized data on the development of conflict resolution skills in future lawyers of experimental and control groups at the beginning and end of the experiment (in %)

Table 1. Distribution by levels of conflict resolution skills development in future lawyers of experimental and control groups at the beginning and the end of the experiment (in %)

Levels of conflict resolution skills Groups	Low		Mid		High	
	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before
Experimental (E1)	12.41	66.67	58.5	33.33	29.08	-
Experimental (E2)	6.34	65.22	48.34	34.78	46.31	-
Control (C)	35.55	66.67	46.66	33.33	17.78	-

As the examination of Table 1, educational environments proposed to cultivate conflict resolution skills in prospective lawyers definitely govern the development of this ability level greatly when vocational training is organized with a systematic focus on the complex usage of the stated educational environments. In particular, we can see that the number of respondents who demonstrated low-level conflict resolution skills at the end of the experiment decreased only by 12.41% and high-level increased by 29.08% in the experimental group E1, whereas decreasing of low-level conflict resolution skills was 6.34% and increasing of high-level was 46.31% in the experimental group E2, where the mentioned educational environments were applied both for teaching in classes, internships and extracurricular educational activities. In the control group, where the second educational environment was applied, we revealed relatively minor changes in the conflict resolution skills level (low level decreased from 66.66% to 35.55%, middle level increased from 33.33% to 46.66%, high level increased from 0% to 17.78%).

The results have shown that the implemented methods of developing the ability to resolve conflict situations are an effective means of pedagogical impact. Indeed, improvement in skills occurred in both groups, but some differences can be observed. In particular, in the experimental group (E2) there was a significant increase in the number of students with a high level, as shown in Figure 2. While in the

experimental group (E1) there was an increase in the number of middle-level students, as shown in Figure 3. Also, in the experimental group (E2), the number of students with a low level of skills decreased the most, as presented in Figure 4.

Comparing the results obtained in the two experimental groups before and after the experiment, we found generally that there were no statistically significant differences between the levels of conflict resolution skills before and after the implementation of the methods. According to the results of the variance analysis (ANOVA), the p-value ($p=0.999$) is significantly higher than 0.05, which allowed us to reject the null hypothesis that there are significant differences. Thus, the results of the analysis indicate that all our methods (for experimental groups E1 and E2) are effective in reducing the number of students with low level and increasing the number of students with a middle level of conflict resolution skills. However, from our point of view, the additional development of pedagogical techniques or modifications of existing ones may be required to increase the number of students with a high level of relevant conflict resolution skills.

Figure 2. Diagram of comparative data on the high-level development of conflict resolution skills in future lawyers of two experimental groups at the end of the experiment (in %)

Figure 3. Diagram of comparative data on the middle-level development of conflict resolution skills in future lawyers of two experimental (E1 and E2) groups at the end of the experiment (in %)

Figure 4. Diagram of comparative data on the low-level development of conflict resolution skills in future lawyers of two experimental (E1 and E2) groups at the end of the experiment (in %)

3.2. Discussion

The results revealed that the designed educational environments positively influence the level of conflict resolution skills development. This is somewhat consistent with the findings of other scholars. They are the connection and interdependence of the studied skills with different social factors [32], [33]; environments and conflict resolution styles that impact the level of conflict resolution skills [32], [34], [35]; components of readiness for conflict management [35]; specific pedagogical conditions applied to improve some personal features which are necessary for conflict resolution skills development [36], [37]. However, while investigating how certain educational environments influence conflict resolution skills development, we did not evaluate the factors (such as caste, gender, and economic condition) considered by Sawant and Magre [32]. It may be seen as our limitation.

Another our finding connected with the design of effective educational environments for developing conflict resolution skills (establishing a cultural atmosphere fostering humane principles, promoting cultural development, and enhancing students' ethical and volitional potentials; equipping future lawyers with a strong theoretical foundation in conflict resolution to develop related competencies; developing educational cases to help learners master conflict resolution skills during vocational training) is in alignment with the results revealed by previous studies [35]–[37] who tested similar environments. The difference with our investigation is that the scholars applied as an educational environment “improving the level of psychological and pedagogical competence among academic staff.” At the same time, we did not organize any special training for our teaching staff. It also may be considered one of our limitations.

Furthermore, we found that conflict resolution skills will be enhanced during classes with special educational cases directed to facilitating the mastery of the mentioned skills, extracurricular activities, as well as internships, and we may agree with Khaliq *et al.* [33] that practice in the future specialty will influence these skills significantly. However, our findings about the role of knowledge in resolving conflicts contradict the results of the scholars that knowledge of conflict resolution style [33] and education in general [34] will not help develop the studied skills. The reason for such discrepancies is probably due to some limitations of our investigation. We did not have separate experimental groups to test the effectiveness of each educational environment designed by us separately. Instead, we did it in complex. So, in our experiment, we provided future lawyers with a foundation in conflict resolution knowledge as a part of educational environments. As a result, we have proved that in the designed complex, a system of knowledge is important and affects the level of conflict resolution skills development.

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, during the study, we revealed that the specially designed educational environments (establishing a cultural atmosphere fostering humane principles, promoting cultural development, and enhancing students' ethical and volitional potentials; equipping future lawyers with a strong theoretical foundation in conflict resolution to develop related competencies; developing educational cases to help

learners master conflict resolution skills during vocational training) are effective for increasing the levels of conflict resolution skills development as the distribution by levels of these skills development in experimental groups changed significantly while in the control group changes were less significant. Herewith, conflict resolution skills are the ability that empowers an individual to swiftly, respectfully, and efficiently address conflicts. While conflict may be understood as a situation that appears between two interconnected parties experiencing strong emotions, with seemingly incompatible outcomes or beliefs, where at least one party recognizes the incompatibility and views it as problematic. We also exposed that conflict resolution skills of a person may consist of some key components such as: i) criterion related to motivation and personal attributes; ii) criterion related to intellectual and cognitive abilities; and iii) criterion related to procedural and reflexive skills.

The implications of our findings may be useful for improving soft skills at the tertiary level (however, different soft skills will need to be applied in different educational environments). As the research has revealed the potency of educational environments for conflict resolution skills development, in the future, it may be helpful to utilize the proposed educational environments in complex within formal educational settings, during extracurricular activities, as well as during internships. The investigation that was carried out does not insist on providing a definitive and comprehensive finding to the issue under study. So, the prospect of the development of research findings may be referred to enhancing the training techniques and technical assistance for cultivating conflict resolution skills in preparing lawyers-to-be. Special attention can be paid to the application prospects of further studies into personal approaches to conflict resolution development and the specific needs of students from different faculties.

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This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

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R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

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Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [LH], on request.

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